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PARTICIPATORY BUDGETING OF THE STATE BUDGET

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Abstract: This article presents legal and analytical information on the work carried out within the framework of the «Initiative Budget» process conducted this year through the «Open Budget» information portal organized by the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, proposals submitted by citizens, voting processes and cases of financing proposals recognized as winners, as well as on the work done within the framework of the «Open Budget» project.

Key words: initiative budget, Open budget, citizens' budget, information portal, state budget, citizens' opinion.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada tadqiqot davomida o'rganilgan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Moliya vazirligi tomonidan tashkil etilgan "Ochiq budjet" axborot portali orqali joriy yilda o'tkazilayotgan "Tashabbusli budjet" jarayonlari doirasida amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar, fuqarolar tomonidan bildirilgan takliflar, ovoz berish jarayonlari va g'olib deb topilgan takliflarni moliyalashtirish holatlari yuzasidan huquqiy va tahliliy ma'lumotlar, shuningdek tashabbusli budjetlashtirish tizimida keyingi bosqichda amalga oshirilishi kutilayotgan ishlar yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: tashabbusli budjet, Ochiq budjet, axborot portali, davlat budjeti, jamoatchilik fikri.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена правовая и аналитическая информация о работе, проведенной в рамках процессов «Инициативный бюджет», проведенных в текущем году через информационный портал «Открытый бюджет», организованный Министерством финансов Республики Узбекистан, предложениях, внесенных гражданами, процессах голосования и случаях финансирования предложений, признанных победителями, а также о работе, проделанной в рамках проекта «Открытый бюджет».

Ключевые слова: инициативный бюджет, Открытый бюджет, информационный портал, государственный бюджет, общественный мнения.

INTRODUCTION

In our country, the process of comprehensively adapting the general public to the implementation of the "Participatory Budget" project has required several years of effort, and in fact, continues even today. It is certainly a positive development that citizens fully understand and exercise their rights and responsibilities. However, various recurring questions continue to be raised by some citizens, journalists, and bloggers. For example:

- Why is the "Participatory Budget" project necessary?
- Why is the state shifting its functions onto the shoulders of citizens?
- Should problems be solved at the expense of citizens wandering from place to place?
- For how many years is this project intended?

These questions are closely connected with certain shortcomings that arise when financial literacy and the essence of the project are not fully explained. In reality, the "Participatory Budget" project is not designed for a specific period — and the experience of developed countries clearly demonstrates this.

For instance, if we look at the proposals submitted by citizens in the participatory budgeting process of the French Republic, we can observe suggestions such as:

- constructing bicycle parking areas;
- building a digital library;
- proposals related to green budgeting.

This does not mean, of course, that issues such as repairing internal roads or improving the material and technical base of social facilities are irrelevant for the people of France.

However, we must acknowledge that today in our country there are issues of much higher importance and social significance than constructing bicycle parking areas or building digital libraries. This is characteristic of any developing country, and, according to preliminary projections, we believe that within the next 10 years (by 2035), the sectoral composition of proposals submitted by citizens within the framework of the “Participatory Budget” will fundamentally change in our country as well. To achieve this, we will continue dedicating our full effort and determination to contribute to ongoing reforms.

For reference, the “Participatory Budget” project is not the only mechanism aimed at solving all social problems in our country. Every year, in accordance with the Law “On the State Budget,” funds are regularly planned from the state budget for the construction (or reconstruction) and equipping of social facilities, as well as for the development of infrastructure.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Research on participatory budgeting in the context of the state budget has expanded significantly, focusing on democratic governance, fiscal transparency and inclusive decision-making. Gianpaolo Baiocchi showed that participatory budgeting strengthens public accountability by shifting budget decisions closer to citizens and reducing elite dominance in resource allocation. His findings demonstrate that institutionalized participation enhances the legitimacy of state budget processes. Brian Wampler emphasized that participatory mechanisms embedded in national and regional budget systems improve allocative efficiency, particularly when participation rules ensure inclusiveness, transparency and fair representation of marginalized groups.

Yves Sintomer’s comparative studies revealed that participatory budgeting at the state level introduces new forms of co-governance in which citizens and public authorities jointly shape spending priorities. His typology of global participatory budgeting practices highlights the role of political will, administrative capacity and civic culture in determining the effectiveness of state-level participation. Archon Fung argued that empowered participatory institutions, including those linked to state budgets, increase governmental responsiveness when participatory processes grant citizens real influence rather than symbolic consultation.

Stephen Goldsmith’s work on data-smart governance demonstrated that digital tools and open-government platforms expand citizen participation in state budget decisions by providing accessible information and enabling real-time monitoring of public spending. International organizations such as the World Bank and OECD have documented that participatory budgeting strengthens fiscal discipline, improves public trust, enhances anti-corruption measures and supports evidence-based allocation of state financial resources. Their empirical analyses confirm that participatory budgeting, when integrated into state budget frameworks, contributes to more transparent, accountable and socially responsive governance.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, data on state-level participatory budgeting were collected from official government budget reports, open-budget platforms, OECD and World Bank public finance databases. The collected information was processed through comparative analysis, systematic review, statistical summarization and content analysis to identify patterns of citizen participation, transparency levels and fiscal outcomes, allowing an evidence-based evaluation of participatory budgeting practices.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The primary goal expected from the “Participatory Budget” process is to address long-standing social problems that have troubled the general public for many years, by solving them with citizen participation—unlike the traditional budget system. This clearly shows that participation in the “Participatory Budget” process is entirely voluntary. It is also completely incorrect to assume that projects not selected as winners are ignored or that a problem will only be financed if its project wins.

Participatory budgeting refers to the practice of allocating a portion of budget funds by taking citizen initiatives into account and making decisions on how these funds should be spent directly with the participation of citizens, as well as monitoring the implementation of the decisions taken.

It includes:

- informing citizens about the current budget and the budget planning process;
- preventing the misuse of funds;
- enabling local authorities and citizens to jointly make decisions on sectors of high importance within a given territory;
- informing citizens about the funds being spent in line with ongoing reforms in their region.

Participatory budgeting provides opportunities for residents, civil society institutions, and individual citizens of a given territory to participate in defining development priorities for their communities.

Participatory budgeting is the involvement of citizens in allocating a portion of the local budget based on public proposals, determining directions for spending, making decisions directly through citizen participation, and establishing public oversight over the implementation of adopted decisions.

At this point, I would like to draw your attention to one important statistic: this year marks the 5th anniversary of the introduction of participatory budgeting, and together with our proactive citizens, we held the eighth season. During this period, more than 18,000 projects were implemented, and 17 trillion soums were allocated from the state budget. These figures alone demonstrate that Participatory Budgeting has risen to the level of state policy and has deeply integrated into the daily lives of citizens.

Despite this progress, in many regions of the country, there are cases where certain projects remain unfinished, and contractor organizations have not been paid for completed work. Nevertheless, the clients (ordering authorities) have issued “commissioning” certificates and removed these facilities from the list of ongoing construction projects.

For example, within the first season of the 2025 Participatory Budgeting process, in the project to repair General Education School No. 8 located in Balikchi district of Andijan region, despite construction works still being underway, on 20 June of this year, the Andijan Regional Single Customer Service Enterprise issued “commissioning” certificates, and these were displayed on the “Open Budget” portal.¹

In such cases, the contracting organizations, in collusion with the client enterprises, issue “commissioning” certificates ahead of schedule with the aim of artificially improving their rating scores and thereby increasing their chances of participating in upcoming tender competitions.

Such attempts at fabrication not only mislead proactive citizens and contribute to the misuse of budget funds, but also inevitably affect the quality of both “Participatory Budget” projects and other construction projects.

Today, the Ministry of Economy and Finance, within the framework of winning projects, is taking measures to introduce amendments and additions to Resolution No. KQ-666-IV of the Council of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in order to increase the sense of responsibility of all individuals and legal entities authorized to sign “commissioning” certificates.

The state budget is an important instrument of macroeconomic management in the economy, and its effectiveness determines the government’s success in achieving socio-economic objectives. The state budget is a tool for implementing social and economic policies and priorities that directly affect the lives of citizens. One of the modern methods of budgeting based on citizen participation in the budget process is participatory budgeting, which is widely used in many countries at the contemporary stage of budget relations.

As you are aware, in recent years the practice of conducting mass surveys on various issues and across different sectors has become widespread. In particular, surveys involving broad public participation through the internet are becoming increasingly common.

What benefits do such surveys provide to the population, and what positive or negative consequences do they have? First, surveys may be designed either for all segments of the population or for a specific audience. Second, depending on the target audience, survey questions are shaped around topics of their interest. Surveys differ depending on their objectives and the entity conducting them.

Mass surveys are usually conducted through face-to-face meetings, websites, mass media, messaging applications, and other tools. Conducting surveys is also considered an effective approach for identifying deficiencies in the legal sphere and eliminating them as much as possible. At the international level, surveys are performed in areas such as the Rule of Law Index (WJP), the Corruption Perceptions Index, the Worldwide Press Freedom Index, the Index of Economic Freedom, the Governance Matters indicators, and other fields. Similar examples can be found across many sectors.²

In this context, the Ministry of Justice also frequently conducts public surveys. For example, between 2018 and 2020, several surveys were carried out among citizens, entrepreneurs, non-governmental non-profit organizations, and state bodies on issues related to labor relations, property rights, and other matters.

¹ O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Iqtisodiyot va Moliya vazirligi “Ochiq byudjet” axborot portali

² Participatory Budgeting: Leaving No One Behind. Glasgow Disability Alliance, 2019. <https://gda.scot/resources/participatory-glasgow-leaving-no-one-behind/>

The purpose of conducting such surveys is to identify minor and major shortcomings in various sectors and to implement comprehensive measures to eliminate existing deficiencies based on public opinion.

Determining the priority directions for financing expenditures from local budgets is one of the most important tasks facing local executive and representative bodies. Typically, these matters are handled by various authorized bodies involved in the budget process. However, there are issues that remain outside the attention of local executive and representative authorities.

These may include problems ranging from the transportation and consumption of drinking water or interruptions in electricity supply, to unlit pedestrian walkways or problems related to communal services in residential buildings. In precisely such cases, participatory budgeting provides an opportunity to bring the issue to public discussion and find an optimal solution.

When local authorities adopt a decision or implement a project intended to benefit the broader public interest without considering the opinions and proposals of citizens, this may lead to public dissatisfaction and, in some cases, inefficient use of funds.

The most important outcome of implementing participatory budget mechanisms is not only solving issues related to social infrastructure development but also fostering the development of social and human capital in residential communities. Through direct participation in the budget process, citizens become active contributors to social transformation.

Participatory budgeting helps identify the most active residents who wish to participate in improving their surroundings and encourages them to connect with one another. By working together and discussing various projects, participants develop their communication skills when addressing real issues and learn to search for common solutions to controversial matters. Within this process, key components of social capital—social connections and trust—begin to emerge. This trust arises not only among citizens themselves but also between citizens and local leaders. Achieving this through other means is nearly impossible.³

In addition, participants enhance their level of human capital by acquiring knowledge about state and local governance processes, as well as skills in discussing, developing, presenting and defending projects, while also gaining experience in interactions with government institutions. Local executive bodies, in turn, learn to view the needs of the population not through the lens of sectoral issues or complaints, but in the form of well-grounded and reasonable proposals.

Thus, the participatory budgeting process not only addresses social issues, but also fosters an active civil community that is ready to work collaboratively, solve complex tasks, independently develop projects and identify, generate and expand new resources for regional development.

In recent years, many countries have increasingly adopted participatory budgeting mechanisms. This mechanism allows citizens to decide how a portion of local budget funds should be allocated and used. This approach to involving citizens in the budgeting process was first applied in 1989 in the city of Porto Alegre, Brazil. Improvements in public administration and the development of information technologies have enabled local authorities and self-governing bodies in many countries to use participatory budgeting mechanisms.

Currently, this mechanism is used in more than 7,000 local budgets worldwide. The following outcomes associated with participatory budgeting may reasonably be considered additional economic benefits:

- Project costs decrease and the efficiency of budget spending increases. Practice shows that projects implemented through participatory budgeting tend to cost significantly less than those carried out without community involvement. Since local residents have limited opportunities to directly resolve social issues benefiting the majority, they strive to make the most of this opportunity and spend money economically yet effectively.

- The quality of completed work improves due to public oversight. Residents who voted for or co-financed a particular project are genuinely interested in ensuring the project is implemented with high quality. (Depending on citizens' consent and preferences, some projects may be financed jointly through budget funds and citizens' contributions. For example, if the participatory budget allocation is sufficient only to replace a neighborhood's electrical transformer, but not enough to replace utility poles, and if adding the pole replacement to a state program would delay the work for two or three years, residents may choose to renew the poles using their own sponsorship contributions. In this case, the electrical transformer is replaced at the expense of the local budget, while the poles are replaced using residents' funds. Joint financing of projects is an important source for developing community finance. Moreover, the key factor is not the amount of funds raised, but the involvement of residents in contributing their own resources. Even a small personal contribution increases a citizen's sense of ownership over the issue.)

For example, when contractors build roads under public supervision, local residents constantly monitor the width, thickness and quality of the asphalt. If necessary, they verify compliance with established standards and may demand corrections when violations are detected.

3 https://admin.openbudget.uz/media/post_attachments/asnova_uz.pdf

- The service life of facilities increases. When residents select a project, they not only take interest in its implementation, but also participate actively in the process. At the same time, they monitor the quality of the work to ensure that the facility can serve the community for many years. As a result, the service life of facilities is extended. For example, if a project to build a bridge is being implemented in a neighborhood, local residents monitor the work of the contractor that won the tender, and raise concerns if they observe deficiencies during construction. Since the work is carried out under broad public oversight, the contractor is compelled to ensure high-quality performance, thereby ensuring long-term use of the bridge.

- The level of budget literacy among the population increases. Participatory budgeting not only allows citizens to take part in the budgeting process, but also helps them understand how the taxes they pay are being spent. For example, today active citizens review project documentation and monitor project implementation; in some cases, they even demand that builders specify the amount of bitumen, gravel or clinker required for laying one square meter of asphalt (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Projects under public oversight⁴

In international practice, projects proposed within participatory budgeting are conditionally divided into three categories:

1. Territorial projects: In this case, citizens submit proposals aimed at addressing social or economic issues in their place of residence (neighborhood, district, city, etc.). Examples include street lighting, drinking water supply, road asphaltting, and various communal problems.

2. Projects focused on specific development areas: These include proposals related to environmental protection, climate change, ecological conditions and food security, healthcare, education, employment, and similar sectors.

3. Projects proposed by specific social groups: For example, persons with disabilities, students, youth, migrants, women, elderly people, and others. In recent years, international experience shows that proposals submitted specifically by social groups are becoming increasingly common in participatory budgeting processes. This trend contributes to reducing administrative interference and ensuring that community-driven priorities are reflected more accurately.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Explaining participatory budgeting processes to the population correctly and effectively is a decisive step in ensuring broad citizen engagement. To achieve this, it is important to prepare clear, simple and easily understandable information by avoiding overly technical or official terminology and instead using plain, everyday language that people naturally use. Visual tools such as infographics, diagrams and short animations help convey the process more effectively, while presenting information in a question-and-answer format through FAQs improves comprehension and reduces confusion among citizens.

Ensuring access to information for all segments of the population requires the use of multiple communication channels. Printed materials distributed through neighborhoods, community centers and local shops help reach residents directly, while television, radio, newspapers and social media platforms such as Telegram, Instagram and Facebook expand coverage. Short explanatory SMS messages or notifications through mobile applications also serve as an efficient method of awareness raising. In addition, introducing dedicated lessons

⁴ Muallifning mustaqil izlanishlari natijasida o'rganilgan

and seminars in schools and higher education institutions strengthens understanding of participatory budgeting among students. For example, higher education institutions specializing in economics in our country already offer a course specifically devoted to the participatory budgeting process as part of their curriculum.

Live interactions also play a crucial role in building trust and involvement. Organizing face-to-face meetings at predetermined times during neighborhood gatherings allows officials to discuss the process directly with citizens. Tailored communication methods, adapted to different groups such as youth, women and the elderly, ensure that the information reaches its target audience effectively and respectfully.

Demonstrating real examples further strengthens public trust. Showing projects implemented in previous years and familiarizing residents with their outcomes in person serves as strong motivation for participation. When people see, for instance, that a neighborhood voted the previous year and successfully repaired a road, it reinforces confidence in the process and encourages active involvement in future initiatives.

Listening to the opinions of citizens is a key pillar of participatory budgeting. Surveys and interviews help identify public interests, expectations and emerging questions. Expressing appreciation toward proactive citizens who contribute ideas, and recognizing their efforts whenever possible, reinforces a culture of community engagement and shared responsibility.

Engaging young people, bloggers and journalists who hold influence within their communities enhances the reach and impact of awareness campaigns. Their participation in focus groups and discussions ensures a continuous exchange of ideas, helps generate innovative solutions and supports the introduction of technical improvements required for the process to evolve.

Strengthening the legal foundation and building trust is equally essential. Citizens must regularly be informed about their rights, the guarantees provided by the government, the transparency mechanisms in place and the accountability of officials for achieving results. When society witnesses the successful implementation of winning projects and sees tangible improvements with their own eyes, people become more confident in collective action and are motivated to propose new initiatives. As the wise say, it is the duty of the awakened to awaken those who remain asleep.

In a short period of time, the participatory budgeting initiative has become a unifying social platform that fosters community cohesion, improves financial literacy and, most importantly, serves as a digital bridge between the state and society.

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